

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

A FEW ASPECTS REGARDING THE EVALUATION AND EXPLOITATION OF ROMANIA'S WIND ENERGY POTENTIAL

Minda Andrea Amalia,

*Ph.D., Lecturer of Babeş-Bolyai University of Cluj-Napoca,
Faculty of Engineering*

Amariei Olga-Ioana,

*Ph.D., Lecturer of Babeş-Bolyai University of Cluj-Napoca,
Faculty of Engineering*

Szabo Emeric-Remus, Negrea Daniela Tabita,

*Ph.D. Students of University of Oradea,
Doctoral School of Engineering Sciences*

Cincar Kristijan ,

Ph.D. Student of West University of Timisoara

Lolea Marius Savu

Ph.D., ACCSISEO of Oradea

Abstract

The paper presents some aspects regarding the identification of the wind potential, the location of the areas with high wind potential and the way of wind energy utilization. At the beginning, details are presented regarding the characteristics of wind energy and aggregates that ensure the conversion of primary wind energy into electricity. Ways of scientific research and evaluation of the energy of the wind and the factors on which the degree of conversion of wind energy into electricity depends are presented. While Romania possesses a significant theoretical wind potential, the practical exploitation of this potential is of greater interest for energy development forecasts. The practical potential is considerably lower than the theoretical potential due to land use constraints and market conditions. The results of the assessment of the possibilities of building wind farms for various areas of the country are presented. Romania's installed wind energy capacity, which is mainly derived from onshore wind farms, has been growing steadily over the past decade. Wind energy has become the country's second-largest renewable energy source, following hydropower. By focusing on these aspects, Romania can effectively evaluate and exploit its wind energy potential to enhance its renewable energy portfolio.

Keywords: Wind energy, energy potential, installed power.

Introduction

Romania could have a renewables target of 34 % at the level of 2030, revised upwards from the previous level of 30.7%, in the context where at the level of the entire European Union it is desired to accelerate investments in green energy. At the EU level, through the REPowerEU program, the alternative renewable target of around 40 % for 2030 was increased to 45% in response to the conflict in Ukraine, with the aim of reducing dependence on Russia through investments in green energy. Wind energy could become the biggest force in the local landscape of energy production in the next decade, with a weight of 30 % of the total mix, over hydro energy, if Romania follows the path of the European program of the European Union (EU), through which aims to accelerate investments in green energy (REPowerEU), with the aim of quickly reducing dependence on Russia.

In 2023, Europe has the installed wind power capacity of 18.3 GW. That's a record amount according to experts, but still about half of what it should build to meet its climate and energy goals for 2030. 79% of the new wind capacity built in Europe last year was onshore. The volume of new offshore installations is in-

creasing – last year there was a record 3.8 GW in Europe. But 2/3 of new wind installations by 2030 will continue to be onshore [9].

Between 2024 and 2030, Europe is expected to install 260 GW of new wind power capacity. The EU-27 should install 200 GW of this – 29 GW per year on average. To meet its 2030 climate and energy targets, the EU now needs to build an average of 33 GW per year to at least meet the 42.5 % renewable energy target in 2030 set before the COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine [10].

Evaluation and conversion of wind energy potential

Wind energy is the kinetic energy of air masses in motion in the earth's atmosphere. Its transformation into electrical energy is done by means of wind aggregates equipped with a turbine-generator system and auxiliary exhaust installations [4].

In general, as it results from the research of the specialized literature, wind turbines are divided into two basic types, as well as the position of the rotor [2]:

- with horizontal axis of rotation of the rotor, Fig. 1.a;
- with vertical axis of rotation of the rotor, Fig. 1.b,c (Ex. types: Derreus-b, Savonius-c).

Fig. 1. Conventional wind turbines: a – with horizontal axis; b and c – with vertical axis.

The most widely used are horizontal axis wind turbines, which are industrially produced and usually installed with powers of about 15 -16 MW.

Fig. 2. The appearance and structure of wind aggregates [1]

The component elements of a wind turbine are shown in figure 2 [1]. These are: Nacelle 6, mounted on pillar 11, contains the main component elements of the turbine. The blades 1 are mounted on the hub 2. The speed amplifier 3 has the role of increasing the required speed of the electric generator 9. In the case of high wind speeds, which can endanger the good operation of the wind turbine, the coupling with the electromagnetic clutch 4, which receives command from the control system 7, can interrupt the rotation of the blades. In case of overheating, the fan 8 reduces the temperature of the system. 5 The anemometer that measures the wind speed; the pivoting system 10 that orients the turbine with the rotor perpendicular to the direction of wind action.

The energy produced in a period by the wind turbine depends on its constructive characteristics and on the wind potential of the area (wind speed) where the turbine is installed.

An approximate formula indicating the monthly energy produced by a wind turbine is the next one [1]:

$$W_1 = \frac{D^2 \cdot v_m^3}{10} \quad (1)$$

In which: W_1 [kWh] represents the energy produced by the turbine in a month; D [m] – rotor diameter; v_m [m/s] – medium speed of wind.

The power of a wind turbine can be determined with the next [2]:

$$P = \frac{1}{2} C_p A V^3 \rho \quad (2)$$

where: P [W] – power of wind generator, C_p – coefficient of the wind generator, determined experimentally for the first time by Berz, and equal to $16/27 = 0,59$, as maximum possible value, A [m²] – the described surface of the wind turbine propeller, at one full rotation, V [m/s] – wind speed, ρ [kg/m³] – air density.

From a technological point of view, of the efficiency of energy production and functionally, some notions of the wind turbine and its location are defined [2]:

- starting speed - the wind speed at which a wind turbine, well defined dimensionally, in terms of type and power, starts delivering useful power to the propeller shaft, is between 3.4 - 5.2 m/s;
- stall speed - the speed at which a well-defined wind turbine no longer delivers useful power to the shaft (stops rotating), is usually below the starting value;
- critical speed - the wind speed at which the protective device mounted on the propeller shaft (if installed), disconnects the turbine in order to avoid technical accidents (due to too high wind blowing intensity), is usually over 27-29 m/s.

The first step in making the decision regarding the realization of an energy project consists in identifying the primary resources and evaluating their energy potential. The case for the adoption of wind conversion systems is also obvious.

If there are resources with high potential, then the final decision on the location of a wind turbine belonging to the financier will be made after carrying out a

feasibility study from the conclusions of which results among others [2]:

- the cost price of the investment
- the investment cost recovery time
- duration of execution of the investment
- the energy efficiency of the investment.

The evaluation of the energy potential of the wind with the obtaining of data necessary for the design, can be done as in the case of other resources, in three ways.

Practical measurements are the first and most recommended way, being also the most sophisticated. For this, a pole is mounted in the chosen location on which several measuring, observation and recording devices are mounted [2]. The duration of the measurements is usually one year, but information is also taken from the meteorological stations that monitor the respective area. Identifying the wind speed can be done practically with the use of devices called anemometers (Fig. 3) [1].

Fig. 3. Combined wind direction and speed determination system [1]

For rapid studies, factors may intervene that prevent the performance of measurements. In these cases, you can use the online web platforms made with satellite data and made available to those who wish for free by relevant institutions. The data is updated regularly and its use is safe. The platforms in question present maps of the wind and its energy parameters. Such a case is the application <globalwindatlas>[9].

The use of the mentioned platform with the identification of wind energy characteristics for a given area is the application of the work. Upon entering the platform, the wind map for the celestial globe is displayed. From there, the desired area will be selected with the help of the computer mouse or from keyboard (Fig.4). Wind intensities will be displayed in color code.

Fig. 4. Access interface in the platform of wind atlas.

For a certain point of location, the identification of the location can also be done by entering the geographical coordinates. The names of the nearest weather station will also be automatically displayed, with the name

of the country and the GPS fix. In the case of the application, the chosen locality is Budureasa from Bihor County, Romania.

Fig. 5. The wind density

and some temporal data for the selected area

The energy parameters that interest the operator can be selected from the dedicated menu bar. Fig. 5 shows the wind density display interface. The measurement height can be adjusted from the magnitude scale

located on the right/bottom of the interface. 5 playback heights are possible, namely: 10 m, 50 m, 100 m, 150 m and 200 m.

Fig. 6. The wind frequency and the mean wind speed for the selected area

Fig. 6 shows the display interface of the wind speed for the selected area. In this, for the chosen height of 100 m, it can be seen that the energy density produced is 269 W/m² and the wind speed is 5,5 m/s.

Conversion efficiency data can also be obtained on certain categories of turbines or different ways of displaying the terrain configuration as well as the wind rose graph for the chosen area.

A third way to obtain data on wind energy parameters is the use of reports or databases from specialized technical literature or from scientific works published in various websites. This way is the least recommended because the data entered there may be perishable under the conditions of recent or future climate changes.

Exploitation of wind energy in Romania

The availability of electricity at the level of a wind power plant depends on several categories of factors: the human factor (which monitors the plants and intervenes quickly in case of malfunctions) environmental factors, mechanical factors and electromagnetic factors (including the components of the process monitoring and adjustment system). The following parameters are involved in harnessing the energy potential of the wind: wind speed, wind duration, turbine orientation, turbine height, reservation (redundancy), air density, energy accumulation, blade surface, inverter efficiency, rotor diameter.

Fig. 7. The flow diagram of the regulation of the availability of the power of the air units in the reference point

But not all the mentioned parameters can be acted upon during operation. In the flow diagram represented in Fig. 7, several adjustable factors are taken into account that influence the availability of electrical energy initiated by the power produced (P_g) by a wind generator.

The parameters considered when creating the flow diagram of the availability of electricity provided by a wind power unit are: the height of the turbine (H), the diameter of the rotor (Dr), the surface of the blade exposed to the wind (Sp), the efficiency of the generator (η), the reservation of escape routes (R) and ensuring

the accumulation of generated electricity (Ae). The orientation of the turbine can ensure a stable exposure of the turbine blades to the right wind.

The installed wind capacities in Romania place it in 10th place in the European Union alongside countries such as Austria and Croatia. The share of electricity production from wind power plants was 14% of the total SEN production for the year 2023 (Fig.8).

The first three countries in the European Union such as the importance regarding the use of wind energy are Denmark (56%), Ireland (36%) and Germany (31%). Without electricity production from wind conversion, until the year 2022, are countries like Switzerland, Slovenia and Slovakia.

Fig. 8. The share of electricity produced in the EU in wind power plants. [8]

Fig. 9 presents statistical data regarding the evolution onshore wind energy capacity in Romania from 2008 to 2022.

Fig. 9. Onshore wind energy capacity in Romania from 2008 to 2022

The installed wind energy capacity in Romania is expected to grow from 3.33 gigawatts in 2024 to 4.12 gigawatts by 2029. The areas with the highest wind energy potential in Romania are primarily the mountain peaks, where wind speeds can exceed 8 meters per second. The second most promising regions are the Black Sea Coast, the Danube Delta, and northern Dobrogea, with average annual wind speeds around 6 meters per second. These areas are also advantageous for wind energy exploitation due to their lower wind turbulence compared to other regions.

The third area with considerable potential is the Bârlad Plateau, where the average wind speed is around 4-5 m/s. Favorable wind speeds are also reported in other smaller areas in the west of the country, in the

Banat area and on the western slopes of the Western Hills [5].

When considering wind energy development forecasts, the focus shifts from the theoretical wind potential to the practical potential for wind energy applications. This practical potential is significantly lower than the theoretical potential, as it depends on factors such as land use feasibility and market conditions. Therefore, the economically viable wind potential can only be estimated in the medium term, using current technological and economic data expected to remain relevant during this period.

The technical and economic wind potential data are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

The wind potential of Romania [4]

Parameter	M.U.	Technic	Economic (2030-2050)
Nominal Power	MW	3600	2400
Electrical Energy	TWh/an	8,0	5,3
	Thousand stoe/year	688	456

The distribution of wind and photovoltaic energy capacities installed in 2022 on the territory of Romania is presented in figure 10, on a so-called "green map". [9].

Fig. 10. Green map of Romania [6]

Fig. 11 shows the electricity situation at a given moment in Romania according to the energy system tracking platform by the national system and transport operator.

Fig. 11.

Chart on the production, consumption and balance of electricity from RPS (Romanian Power System) [6]

At the time of the study for one day in May 2024, the production from wind power plants was in the 4th place in Romania with a share of 11.2% of the total of 4745 MW of power in function. The largest wind farms in Romania, at the time of the study, are [10]: 1. Fântânele Vest – 262,5 MW (Constanța County), 2. Coșgealac – 252 MW (Constanța County), 3. Făcăeni – 132 MW (Ialomița County), 4. Pantelimon – 123 MW (Constanța County), 5. Târgușor – 119,6 MW (Constanța County), 6. Crucea Nord – 108 MW (jud. Constanța), 7. Peștera – 90 MW (Constanța County), 8. Topolog-Dorobanțu – 84 MW (Tulcea County), 9. Chirnogeni – 80 MW (Constanța County), 10. Mihai Viteazu IV – 80 MW (Constanța County).

Conclusions

Wind energy has already proven to be a very good solution to solving the global energy problem of the present and future.

The complete elimination of polluting waste resulting from the burning of fuels from the energy industry and from all other industries in the shortest possible time is a mandatory task in the context of sustainable development. The production of wind energy does not involve the production of any kind of waste, as such there are no waste expenses, compared to other types of power plants that burn classic polluting fuels, such as thermal power plants. If we consider the huge storage pits for the ash resulting from the burning of coal, the problems raised by the transport of the ash to the warehouse, we can easily realize the proportions of the advantage of using wind energy.

Both centralized energy production and distribution have great disadvantages in terms of the magnitude of energy losses and illegal evasion. Wind energy is among the forms of renewable energy that lend themselves to small-scale, individual production applications. In this context, the introduction of low-power wind systems in the financing programs of the "Green House" type prosumers, next to the photovoltaic installations, both in the areas where it is possible to connect to the public electricity networks and in the isolated ones, is recommended. The cost of electricity produced in modern wind power plants has dropped substantially in recent years, becoming in some countries the most cost-effective source of electricity.

Even if it has a wind energy potential that allows the realization of new capacities, the accentuated dynamics of its exploitation through the rapid and ambitious installation of wind power plants on the territory of Romania led to the impossibility of taking over the electricity produced by the power system. In this regard, it is necessary to install new lines for the evacuation and transport of electricity together with the installation of electrical transformation stations that allow the interconnection of wind power plants with the Electricity public system.

Romania's total installed wind energy capacity is predominantly from onshore wind farms. Over the past decade, wind energy production in Romania has been steadily increasing. Currently, wind energy is the second-largest renewable energy source in the country, following hydropower.

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